

The Influence of Promotion Opportunities and Professional Development on the Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in the Central Region of Botswana

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of promotion opportunities and professional development on the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana. The quantitative approach was used as the method of analysis. A 5 Likert scale Teacher job satisfaction questionnaire (TJSQ) was used to collect data from 206 secondary school teachers in nine secondary schools in the Central region of Botswana. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire was established before it was administered to the teacher respondents. In order to ensure that the instrument was correct and effective, a pilot study which consisted of 15 teachers not included in the actual study was conducted. The Statistical Packages of Social Scientists (SPSS) version 23 was used during the data analysis. The data was then presented through the use of descriptive statistics, One-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and independent sample t-tests tables. The findings of the study showed that the male secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are not satisfied with their job and promotion opportunities when compared to their female counterparts. The study further revealed that secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are significantly satisfied with the provision of professional development in their various schools. The study recommended that the government should promote gender equality in the teaching profession especially during the times of promotion.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Promotion opportunities, Professional development

Introduction

Job satisfaction is a crucial aspect in the improvement of teacher welfare, the quality of teaching as well as the student performance. According to Choi and Tang (2011) teacher job satisfaction contributes to teacher well-being and improves teacher practice (Katharina and Eveline, 2013). Several studies have found teacher job satisfaction significantly linked to job-related variables including; professional development, promotion and the school working conditions (Crossman & Harris, 2006).

Many researchers believe that job satisfaction is likely to influence how employees behave at work, their productivity, employee work effort and even turnover (Mugweru, 2013). Teacher job satisfaction therefore may have serious implications for the school development and the teachers themselves. Ma and MacMillan (2001) highlighted that job dissatisfaction can influence teacher absenteeism, turnover and school effectiveness. If the employees are satisfied with their job, they are likely to be of benefit to the organisation, as low turnover and higher productivity could be assured (Zhongshan, 2007).

According to Iqbal, Aziz, Farooqi and Ali (2016) the teachers who experience higher levels of job satisfaction are likely to be committed to their job in order to bring about high productivity. Therefore, satisfied teachers may offer improved teaching than those who are not content with their job (Iqbal et al., 2016). Moreover, some studies have found that the teachers who are dissatisfied show lower commitment in the school activities (Collie, Shapka, & Perry, 2012; Reeves, Pun & Chung, 2017; Spector, 1997). Such teachers might leave the teaching profession before the retirement age (Collie et al., 2012). When the job satisfaction of teachers is enhanced, their mental health and well-being are improved, and this promotes work motivation, commitment and job performance, thereby reducing teacher attrition and turnover rate (Ingersoll, 2001; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011).

In addition, other studies found that low job satisfaction is often linked to feelings of sadness, despair, anger, bitterness and ineffectiveness (Pinder, 2008). Thus, low job satisfaction negatively impacts on the teacher and the education system as a whole (Pinder, 2008). As a result, it is pertinent for organisations, schools inclusive, to provide employees with satisfactory working environments in order to enhance their job satisfaction and improve productivity in their organisations (Spector, 1997).

When employees' salaries are attractive, they are likely to think that their organisation values them, and this could positively influence their job satisfaction and commitment at work, thereby improving their work performance (Fetogang & Monyamane, 2019). Motivated teachers are therefore more likely to motivate students to learn in the classroom, and also enhance learner performance (Choi & Tang, 2011). There are different factors that may influence secondary teachers' level of job satisfaction. Some of the factors include: the level of teacher salaries, teacher promotion opportunities, professional development of teachers as well as the quality of teachers' working conditions, among others (Katharina and Eveline, 2013).

There is a significant relationship between promotion opportunities, professional development and teacher job satisfaction. As such, it was significant for this study to be conducted in order to establish such correlation in order to inform some recommendations geared towards improving teacher job satisfaction in secondary schools in Botswana as a whole.

Literature Review

Gender, Promotion opportunities and teacher job satisfaction

Teacher promotion is a significant factor of job satisfaction (Wong, 2009). Promotion is when a teacher is moved from a lower rank to a higher position at work with increased responsibility, position and salary (Wong, 2009). Promotions as indicated by Fetogang and Monyamane (2019) provide employees with the opportunities for growth, increased responsibility as well as improved social status. Some studies have established that secondary teachers are dissatisfied with promotion opportunities as they have been in the same lower positions for many years (Hanushek, Kain & Rivkin, 2004; Monyamane & Monyamane, 2019; Monyatsi, 2012).

Mhozya (2007) interviewed junior secondary school teachers in Botswana and found that only 15% of the respondents were satisfied with promotion opportunities. Many of the participants were not satisfied by how promotions were conducted. Another study by Monyatsi (2012) established that most secondary school teachers in Botswana were dissatisfied with insufficient promotion opportunities they had. It is therefore important to note that previous studies had linked promotion opportunities to teacher job satisfaction.

Moreover, quite a number of research studies were conducted to compare the job satisfaction and promotion opportunities of male and female teachers in various contexts (Mabekoje, 2009). In some reviewed literature, no significant difference was found between the job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers while in several studies, it was found that male teachers are more satisfied with their teaching job and promotion opportunities than their female counterparts (Kim, 2005). However, some research findings have shown different results in which female teachers were found to be more satisfied with the teaching job and promotion than males (Clark, 1997).

Despite that the relationship between gender, promotion and job satisfaction has been investigated broadly; the findings of many studies have not been consistent (Clark, 1997). While some studies established that female teachers were more satisfied with their work and promotion opportunities than male ones, others showed that male teachers were more satisfied than females (Crossman & Harris, 2006; Lehman & Stockard, 2004; Fetogang & Monyamane, 2019; Ma & McMillan, 2001).

A study among Canadian teachers revealed that the job satisfaction levels on the promotion opportunities vary significantly between male and female teachers (Ma & MacMillan, 2001). A similar study in the United States of America showed significant differences in the levels of job satisfaction between male and female teachers (Rhodes, 2006). It was established that female teachers were more satisfied with their job than male teachers. Zhongshan (2007) found that male secondary teachers in Shanghai, China were more satisfied with their promotion than their female counterparts. On the contrary, a study by Crossman and Harris (2006) on job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in the United Kingdom indicated that their satisfaction levels were not significantly different by gender.

Since job satisfaction and commitment can determine employee performance, productivity and turnover, the school authorities should seek to improve teacher job satisfaction through providing teachers with promotion opportunities in order to enhance organisational efficiency and work performance (Chamundeswari, 2013).

Maforah (2010) pointed out that South African female Middle and high school teachers consider the lack of promotion to be a significant factor that hugely contributes to teacher job dissatisfaction amongst them. The female teachers in the study reported that they felt largely dissatisfied with their career as they were not given the opportunity to improve it further through promotions (Maforah, 2010).

Professional development and teacher job satisfaction

In the educational settings, it is important for teachers' skills, knowledge, and expertise and learning procedures to be taken into account for the betterment of the education quality (Pas, Bradshaw & Hershfeldt, 2012). It is therefore vital for teachers to be up to date with the contemporary ideas, thinking and methodologies in order to match the 21st century type of education (Kett, International, By-laws, Yang Hansen, Gustafsson, Looney & Sykes, 2011). As such, governments and the school authorities should advocate for professional growth among teachers to enhance their job satisfaction and encourage effective teaching and learning environments (Freund, 2005).

Professional development as part of teacher education as highlighted by Poekert (2012), consists of several examples, including among others; formal education, in-service training, induction programmes, teacher co-operation, individual research, qualification programmes, workshops, seminars, mentoring as well as peer observation and feedback. Moreover, the desire for career growth by the secondary school teachers was found to predict teacher job satisfaction. In a study by Iwu, Ezeuduj, Iwu, Ikebuaku and Tengeh (2018), it was established that the teachers who had been exposed to professional training and development reported high levels of job satisfaction than those who had been in the teaching career but not given such opportunity. Iwu et al. (2018) highlighted that the teachers who had been provided with the opportunities of professional development indicated that they were always prepared for the challenges they encountered in the classroom. The respondents recommended that teachers should be provided with continuous professional development for them to be inspired to teach with confidence (Iwu et al., 2018).

Richardson (2014) pointed out that when teachers are continuously offered with professional development, it affects on the way in which they practice teaching and their overall job satisfaction. Literature further suggests that there is need for teachers to be equipped with relevant knowledge and skills through continual professional development in order for them to be able to address all the challenges associated with the 21st century education system. This according to Cameron (2011) could enhance teachers' confidence thereby improving their job satisfaction and handle any subject matter with confidence.

According to Knox (2011), professional development activities have a significant impact on the teachers' teaching practices behaviour, teacher retention, teachers' self-efficacy and on their job satisfaction. Kett (2014) argued that professional development encourages flexibility in teaching by allowing teachers to adapt with the working situation they are in. This is likely to motivate both the teaching fraternity employees and employers to continue promoting some creativity during the teaching and learning process, thus improving effectiveness in the classroom and learner performance (Kett, 2014).

Research questions

1. What significant relationship is there between gender, promotion opportunities and teacher job satisfaction among teachers in secondary schools?
2. To what extent does professional development significantly influence the job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools?

Research Hypothesis

H_{A1}: There is a significant relationship between gender, promotion opportunities and teacher job satisfaction.

H_{A3}: Professional development significantly influences the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Data Presentation, Interpretation and Analysis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between gender, promotion opportunities and teacher job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics on the Influence of Gender on the Promotion Opportunities of Secondary Schools teachers in the Central Region of Botswana.

Group statistics

Variables	Gender of respondents	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Promotion opportunities	Male	76	4.36	2.43
	Female	78	5.63	3.05

When testing the hypothesis, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to find out how gender influences the promotion opportunities of secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana. The findings of the study revealed that male teachers were not satisfied with their promotion opportunities when compared to their female counterparts. This was supported by the mean of 4.36 for male secondary school teachers and 5.63 for females. These results indicate that most of the teachers who received promotions the Central region of Botswana were females. The null hypothesis was therefore maintained.

H₀₂: The Promotional positions of secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana have no significant influence on their Job Satisfaction and Professional development

Table 2

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the Influence of Promotional positions (Prom P) on the Job Satisfaction and professional development of secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana

Variable	Prom P	n	\bar{X}	SD	Source of variation	SS	Df	ms	F	Sig
Job satisfaction	S/Head	11	22.73	2.76	Between Groups	406.25	4	101.56	8.78	.005
	Head Of Dept	14	20.93	3.71						
	Snr Teacher I	26	17.62	6.41	Within Groups	3939.15	149	26.40		
	Snr Teacher II	95	17.73	5.18						
	Ass Teacher	8	21.00	4.31						
Professional development	S/Head	11	20.09	4.78	Between Groups	208.71	4	52.18	2.33	.059
	Head Of Dept	14	19.64	2.79						
	Snr Teacher I	26	16.46	5.59	Within Groups	3344.42	149	22.45		
	Snr Teacher II	95	17.35	4.80						
	Ass Teacher	8	20.00	3.21						

Table 2 shows how the promotional positions of secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana significantly influence their job satisfaction and professional development.

This trend was tested statistically using Fisher's Least Significance Difference (LSD) test, and it was established that the School Heads are the least satisfied with their job (M=22.73) than the Senior Teacher I teachers (M=17.62). A mean of 20.09, further showed that the School Heads are not provided with adequate professional development when compared to the teachers in the Senior Teacher I position (M=16.46).

Table 3

One Sample t-Test Analysis of the level of Teachers Promotion Opportunities and professional development

Variable	μ	\bar{X}	SD	Mean Diff	t-value	Sig
Promotion Opportunities	17.5	5.00	2.82	-2.00	-8.80	.526
Professional development	17.5	17.75	4.82	247	.635	

$p < .05$ (2-tailed).

When it came to how teachers perceived the provision of promotion opportunities, the findings showed a negative t-value of -8.80 which was found to be significant at .05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis has been maintained. The results imply that the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are not pleased with the opportunities they have on promotions.

Moreover, the study gave a t-value of .635 which was found to be insignificant at .05 alpha level with regard to the professional development of secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana. This implied that the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana were content that they were provided with satisfactory opportunities for professional development. This indicated that teachers are happy with the professional training and development they are provided with. For this reason, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

Discussion

In the past, there was a general feeling that women should be less satisfied with their job and promotion opportunities than men as they occupied on lower positions and usually received lower salary (Fetogang & Monyamane, 2019). However, the findings of this study revealed that secondary school male teachers in the Central region of Botswana are not satisfied with their promotion opportunities when compared to their female counterparts. To support these findings, the mean of 4.36 was found for male teachers while 5.63 was established for female teachers. The similar findings were established in the United States of America where female teachers were found to be more satisfied with their job and promotion opportunities than males (Turner, 2007). The study further established that females were committed to the job than male teachers (Turner, 2007). The education sector and schools in particular as argued by Clark (1997) have more females than males, which was why such results were found. Through these findings therefore, it was revealed that gender is significantly related to job satisfaction.

Contrary to these research findings, a research conducted by Wangai (2012) revealed that female secondary school teachers were less satisfied with their promotion opportunities than the male teachers. Wangai (2012) highlighted that most of the secondary school teacher in higher positions were males and only a few were females. The study findings of Acker (1995) further concluded that female teachers are likely to be more satisfied with their teaching career and promotion, whereas men tend to be more likely than women to stay in teaching profession. The study therefore concluded that female secondary school teachers perceive the teaching job as a suitable and enjoyable profession for them (Acker, 1995).

In a different study, Gedefaw (2012) found that many males than female teachers sought to be in the leadership positions such as Heads of departments, Deputy Principal and Principal. Those who wanted to hold the school management positions were mostly males, 61.6% while females were 38.5%. This indicated that males occupied most of the promotion positions in the schools understudy. If many male teachers held higher positions than their female counterparts, it was likely that they experienced high levels of job satisfaction than females (Osawe, 2015).

On the other hand, the School Heads indicated that they were not provided with sufficient professional development when compared to those in the position of Senior Teacher I. In support of these study findings, Fetogang and Monyamane (2019) quoted Conjoh, Taylor-Morgan, Sesay, Mbayo and Sesay (2017) who conducted a survey comparing the satisfaction of the School Heads and junior teachers with regard to their professional development. The survey found that the School Heads were the least happy with regard to their professional development when compared to those in the junior teacher positions (Fetogang & Monyamane, 2019). The survey of Conjoh et al. (2017) also revealed a strong link between job satisfaction and the task responsibility, task importance, and discretionary authority associated with the position of the secondary schools Principals.

This study has found that the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are happy that they were provided with satisfactory professional development. A t-value of .635 was found to be insignificant at .05 alpha level. This showed that teachers are satisfied with how they are equipped with the skills and knowledge relevant for the ever-changing and challenging curriculum in the education system. The study conducted by Akpan (2017) on work-related variables of institutional commitment of secondary schools in Cross River state in Nigeria agrees with this study findings that teachers are satisfied with the professional training they are provided. Akpan's (2017) revealed that professional development significantly relates to teacher job satisfaction and commitment. The positive relationship of these two variables revealed that when teachers are provided with continual professional development, their level of satisfaction is likely to improve, thereby positively affecting their productivity and commitment at work.

Similarly, a study by Mensah (2012) found that teachers were content with professional development given to them. The study established a strong link between teacher job satisfaction and professional development. Meysan and Ali (2013) reported that if teachers are satisfied with their job and the provision of professional development, they tend to put more effort in their work in order to improve work performance and learner results.

Conclusion

Teacher job satisfaction is of paramount importance to the success of any educational institution. It leads to improved performance and desired teacher well-being, thereby decreasing teacher attrition, absenteeism, stress and burnout. Therefore, it is pertinent for organisations, including secondary schools to take into account all factors which might affect the job satisfaction of employees. The promotion opportunities and professional development are amongst the significant variables that should not be ignored in order to enhance teacher job satisfaction in secondary schools. This study found that the male secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are not satisfied with their job, particularly their promotion opportunities. Moreover, a strong link between job satisfaction, promotion opportunities and gender has been established by this study. As a result, female teachers have been found to be more satisfied with their job than their male counterparts. However, the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana have been found to be satisfied with the professional development they are provided in their respective schools.

Recommendations

The government should promote gender equality in the teaching profession especially during the times of promotions.

The School heads should be given the opportunities for professional training.

There should be high positions created for the School Heads since they revealed that they are not satisfied with the promotion opportunities they have.

Future Research

- A comparative study of teacher job satisfaction in Public and Private secondary schools in Botswana.

- An empirical research on the relationship between teacher well-being, learner performance and job satisfaction among teachers in remote areas in Botswana.
- Teaching English Language as a second language in the rural parts of Botswana.

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